

Structure of Mukonidine*

D. P. CHAKRABORTY, S. ROY and R. GUHA

Bose Institute, Calcutta-700 009

The structure of mukonidine, a carbazole alkaloid has been shown to be 2-hydroxy-3-carbomethoxy carbazole (I).

IN continuation of our studies on carbazole alkaloids from *Murraya koenigii* Spreng, the richest source of different structural types of carbazole alkaloids¹, we now report the structure of a new carbazole alkaloid from the stem bark of the same plant.

The petroleum ether (60-80°) extract of the stem bark of *M. koenigii* on chromatographic separation over neutral alumina furnished a crystalline phenolic carbazole named mukonidine (I), C₁₄H₁₁NO₃ (M⁺ 241), m.p. 245°. It showed in its IR spectrum an-NH-function (3430 cm⁻¹), a chelated hydroxyl group (3200 cm⁻¹), an aromatic ester carbonyl function (1640 cm⁻¹), and aromatic residue (1610, 1510 cm⁻¹). Its UV spectrum was very similar to that of 2-hydroxy carbazole-3-carboxylic acid².

The high intensity base peak at *m/e* 240 (M-1) (a) in the mass spectrum of mukonidine was consistent with the presence of a phenolic hydroxyl group in I. The other significant peaks were at *m/e* 225 (a-CH₃), *m/e* 181 (a-COOCH₃) and *m/e* 153 (a-COOCH₃-CO); the last one was previously observed in glycosoline³ and mukonine⁴.

Mukonidine on methylation with diazomethane gave (II), m.p. 205° (M⁺ 269), the UV spectrum of which was similar to that of 2-methoxycarbazole-3-methyl carboxylate². On reduction with LiAlH₄, (II) furnished 2-methoxy-3-methylcarbazole⁵ (III), m.p. 225°. On alkaline hydrolysis mukonidine furnished 2-hydroxy-carbazole-3-carboxylic acid² (IV), m.p. 269°.

- | R ¹ | R ² |
|----------------|---|
| (I) OH | COOMe |
| (II) OMe | COOMe |
| (III) OMe | CH ₃ |
| (IV) OH | COOH |
| (V) OH | CONHC ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ |
| (VII) OH | CH ₃ |

Therefore, mukonidine could be represented by the structure I which has been confirmed by its synthesis from naphthol-B (V). 2-Hydroxycarbazole-3-carboxylic acid (IV) obtained by the alkaline hydrolysis of (V) on partial methylation (CH₃OH/H₂SO₄) gave a crystalline homogeneous compound, m.p. 242-45° identical with mukonidine in all respects.

Murraya koenigii Spreng has been found to elaborate pyranocarbazoles like girinimbine (VI). Popli *et al.*⁶ suggested that in its formation, 2-hydroxy-3-methylcarbazole (VII) plays a prominent role. The isolation of mukonidine provides a strong circumstantial evidence for the above idea. Evidently in (I), the Ar-C-Me group of (VII) has been oxidised to carbomethoxy group.

Experimental

Isolation of mukonidine (I): One kg of air-dried finely powdered stem-bark of *M. koenigii* Spreng. was Soxhleted for 48 hr with petroleum ether (60-80°). The solvent was then distilled off. The residue left was taken in benzene and chromatographed over alumina. The chloroform eluent on evaporation gave an oily residue which on repeated crystallisation from benzene-chloroform gave a colourless homogeneous solid, mukonidine, m.p. 245°. R_f 0.35 (in 5% methanolic benzene); λ_{max}(EtOH) 230, 248, 266, 272, 308, 316, 323 nm with log ε 4.8, 4.57, 4.64, 4.73, 3.88, 3.78 & 3.18 respectively; Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₁NO₃: C, 69.69; H, 4.61; N, 5.81%; Found: C, 69.70; H, 4.60; N, 5.81%.

O-Methylmukonidine (II): A cold ethereal solution of CH₃N₂ was added to mukonidine (15 mg) in CH₃OH at 0-5°. The mixture was kept overnight in refrigerator. After working up the reaction mixture a colourless homogeneous compound (II), m.p. 205° was obtained; λ_{max}(EtOH) 227, 250, 255.5, 285 nm with log ε 4.5, 4.28, 4.1, 4.13; Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₃NO₃: C, 70.56; H, 5.12; N, 5.52%; Found: C, 70.58; H, 5.13; N, 5.49%.

LiAlH₄ reduction of O-methylmukonidine (II): A solution of O-methyl mukonidine (50 mg) in dry

*Part 44 in Chemical (Molecular) Taxonomy: Part 43, D. P. Chakraborty, A. Islam and S. Roy, *Phytochemistry*, 1978 (in press). Partly presented at the 4th Indo-Soviet Symposium on the Chemistry of Natural Products held at Lucknow, India 1976.

THF (5 ml) was added to a suspension of LiAlH_4 (75 mg) in dry THF and the resulting solution was stirred for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up by decomposing the excess reagent by acidification (5% HCl) and extracting with ether. Removal of ether gave an oily residue which on repeated crystallisation from benzene gave a homogeneous solid, m.p. 225° [λ_{max} (EtOH) 238, 260, 302 nm with $\log \epsilon$ 4.45, 4.34, 3.84 respectively]. The compound was found to be identical with 2-methoxy-3-methyl carbazole⁵ (III) (m.p., m.m.p., UV).

Hydrolysis of mukonidine: formation of (IV): Mukonidine (50 mg) was dissolved in 10% alc. KOH (5 ml) and refluxed on water bath for 5 hr. The alcohol of the mixture was then removed on water bath keeping the volume of the solution unchanged by adding water. The solution was then acidified with HCl. The residue obtained was washed with water, dried and then crystallised from ethyl acetate-benzene mixture, when (IV), m.p. 269° was obtained. Calc. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_3$: C, 68.70; H, 3.93; N, 6.19%; Found: C, 68.72; H, 3.99; N, 6.16%.

Synthesis of mukonidine from naphthol-B (V):
(i) *Formation of 2-hydroxycarbazole-3-carboxylic acid from (V):* The naphthol-B (50 mg) was hydrolysed with 10% KOH solution (5 ml) by refluxing on a water bath for 2 hr. After working up the reaction product, a residue was obtained which was washed, with water

dried and crystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate-benzene when a compound (IV), m.p. 269° was obtained.

(ii) *Partial methylation of (IV) to (I):* A solution of (IV) (20 mg) in MeOH (2 ml) was refluxed in the presence of one drop of conc. H_2SO_4 for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was diluted with 5% NaHCO_3 and extracted with ether. After removal of the solvent a solid residue was obtained which on repeated crystallisation from benzene pet. ether gave (I).

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